

Draft Genome Sequence of *Serratia marcescens* Strain INTA SS310-13 Isolated from Agricultural Soil in Argentina

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Abstract

We report the draft genome sequence of *Serratia marcescens* strain INTA SS310-13, a soil bacterium exhibiting nematicidal, insecticidal, and antifungal activities. Genome analyses confirmed its taxonomic placement within *S. marcescens* and identified genes associated with biocontrol-related traits, including chitinases, extracellular proteases, hemolysins, a complete Type VI secretion system, siderophore systems, bacteriocins, and quorum-sensing regulators. AntiSMASH analysis revealed several biosynthetic gene clusters, including prodigiosin, NRPS-containing, siderophore-associated, microcin H47-like, and RiPP clusters. The assembled genome comprises 4,931,134 bp distributed across 28 contigs with a GC content of 59.84%.

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Serratia marcescens is a Gram-negative bacterium with a remarkable secondary metabolism, capable of producing a wide range of bioactive compounds with antagonistic, nematicidal, insecticidal, and antifungal activities (Soenens & Imperial, 2020; Akhtar et al., 2025). Its biocontrol potential has been documented across diverse agricultural contexts, encompassing suppression of plant-parasitic nematodes, phytopathogenic fungi, and insect pests (Someya et al., 2001; Soenens & Imperial, 2020; Akhtar et al., 2025).

Strain INTA SS310-13 was isolated in June 2018 from a soil sample collected in a family vegetable garden cultivating lettuce affected by plant-parasitic nematodes in Merlo, Buenos Aires Province, Argentina. The strain was isolated on ISP4 agar plates during the isolation of actinobacteria and produced characteristic, red-pigmented colonies on nutrient agar after 24 h of incubation at 29°C. The red pigmentation is consistent with prodigiosin production, a trait restricted to environmental isolates of *S. marcescens* and known to be temperature-dependent, with optimal production occurring below 30°C (Sakuraoka et al., 2019). Based on its nematicidal, insecticidal, and antifungal activities, strain INTA SS310-13 was selected for further characterization.

Genomic DNA was extracted using the Wizard Genomic DNA Purification Kit (Promega). Paired-end libraries (2 × 150 bp) were prepared and sequenced on an Illumina platform at Genomics Unit of the National Institute of Agricultural Technology (INTA, Argentina).

Reads were *de novo* assembled with SPAdes (Bankevich et al., 2012) through the KBase platform (Arkin et al., 2018). Genome completeness and contamination were assessed using CheckM (Parks et al., 2015). Species delineation was carried out using the pubMLST and TYGS (Meier-Kolthoff & Göker, 2019). For phylogenetic analysis, digital DNA–DNA hybridization (dDDH) values were calculated using TYGS (Meier-Kolthoff & Göker, 2019), and Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) analyses were performed using JSpeciesWS (Richter et al., 2016). Genome annotation was performed using RASTtk (Aziz et al., 2008; Brettin et al., 2015). Biosynthetic gene clusters were predicted using antiSMASH (Blin et al., 2019).

Assembly statistics are summarized in Table 1. The genome assembly exhibited high completeness and no detectable contamination, indicating that it provides a reliable representation of the genetic content of strain INTA SS310-13. Despite being a draft assembly, its quality is sufficient for gene prediction, functional annotation, and comparative genomic analyses.

Table 1. Assembly statistics for *Serratia marcescens* strain INTA SS310-13.

Feature	Value
Genome size (bp)	4,931,134
Number of contigs	28
Largest contig (bp)	1,104,544
GC content (%)	59.84
N50 (bp)	401,065
L50	4
Genome completeness (%)	99.81
Genome contamination (%)	0.0
Protein-coding sequences (CDSs)	4,721

Genome-based taxonomic analyses placed strain INTA SS310-13 within *S. marcescens*. Initial taxonomic assignment using PubMLST identified strain INTA SS310-13 as *S. marcescens* with 96% confidence based on comparisons with reference genomes, which was subsequently confirmed by TYGS. Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) analyses performed using JSpeciesWS yielded values of 99.5% (ANIf) and 99.3% (ANIm), while digital DNA–DNA hybridization (dDDH) analysis yielded a value of 95.4% relative to *S. marcescens* subsp. *marcescens* ATCC 13880, confirming the affiliation of strain INTA SS310-13 with this species.

Genome annotation of *S. marcescens* INTA SS310-13 revealed multiple genes potentially involved in biocontrol-related activities, including chitinases, extracellular proteases, hemolysins, a complete Type VI secretion system (T6SS), siderophore biosynthesis and transport systems, bacteriocin production proteins, biofilm-associated determinants, and quorum-sensing regulators. The T6SS is recognized as an important competitive fitness

determinant in the genus *Serratia*, mediating both interbacterial competition and interactions with eukaryotic hosts (Li et al., 2015). Quorum sensing in *S. marcescens* coordinates the production of several virulence and biocontrol-related traits, including prodigiosin, proteases, and biofilm formation (Sakuraoka et al., 2019).

AntiSMASH analysis revealed several biosynthetic gene clusters potentially associated with ecological fitness and biocontrol activity, including a high-confidence prodigiosin biosynthetic cluster, multiple NRPS-containing clusters, siderophore-associated clusters related to viobactin and chrysobactin/trichrysobactin biosynthesis, a microcin H47-like cluster, and an azole-containing RiPP cluster. The prodigiosin cluster is of particular interest given its well-documented antifungal activity and its synergistic interaction with chitinolytic enzymes against phytopathogenic fungi (Someya et al., 2001). Chrysobactin/trichrysobactin-type siderophore gene clusters have been previously identified in environmental *S. marcescens* strains with biocontrol potential (Khilyas et al., 2019). Together with genes encoding chitinases, extracellular proteases, hemolysins, siderophore transport systems, bacteriocins, quorum-sensing regulators and a complete Type VI secretion system, these features provide a genomic basis for the previously reported nematicidal, insecticidal and antifungal activities of strain INTA SS310-13.

Collectively, the genomic features identified in strain INTA SS310-13 reveal a diverse repertoire of determinants associated with antagonism, microbial competition, and host interactions. These findings provide genomic support for its previously reported biocontrol activity and establish a foundation for future studies aimed at elucidating the molecular mechanisms underlying its activity against plant-parasitic nematodes, insect pests, and phytopathogenic fungi.

Data Availability

This Whole Genome Shotgun project has been deposited at GenBank under the accession number JZEMR000000000.

BioProject: PRJNA1477192

BioSample: SAMN60747440

Additional bioinformatic outputs, genome annotation files, and supplementary sequence data generated during this study are available in a companion dataset associated with this genome report.

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Keywords

Agricultural microbiology; microbial genomics; comparative genomics; microbial biocontrol; microbial bioinputs; biocontrol agents; agricultural biotechnology.

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